

SUSTAINING ECONOMIES AND ENHANCING DYNAMIC STRUCTURES

**DELIVERABLE D5.1
AGRONOMIC TRIAL BEST PRACTICES
GUIDELINES**

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History of changes

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0.1	Salah Benyoussef	24/06/2024	Draft
0.2	Abennour Sebei	30/06/2024	Draft
0.3	Noura Omri	15/07/2024	Draft
0.4	Salah Benyoussef	18/07/2024 (Web meeting with MENA representatives)	Draft
0.5	Salah Benyoussef	11/10/2024 (Marrakech Meeting)	Presented during the meeting and last modifications taken into account
0.6	Noura Omri	07/02/2025	First version
0.7	Giuseppe Salvio	24/02/2025	Revised version
0.8	Noura Omri	27/02/2025	Minor modifications
1.0	Giuseppe Salvio	28/02/2025	Final version

Abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation / Acronym	Description
AG	Ancient cereal genotypes
AUDPC	Area Under Disease Progress Curve
EC	Electrical conductivity
EU	Experimental units
HI	Harvest index
Hr	Humidity relative
MC	Modern cereal cultivar
MDI	Mass Disease Index
MENA	Middle East and North Africa
N.A.	Not available
N/ha	Nitrogen per hectare
NDVI	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index
Ph	Potential of hydrogen
T	Temperature
T/ha	Tonnes per hectare
Tan	Total accumulated nitrogen
WUE	Water Usage Effectiveness

Executive Summary

Agronomic trials include a set of experimental trials to be conducted through MENA countries over two consecutive cropping years from M6 to M31 with the production of two deliverables D5.1 and D5.2. In the current report (D5.1), we develop a practical, simplified and comprehensive guide that partners involved in WP5 should follow for setting up, monitoring and collecting data from the agronomic trials to be carried out on ancient grains during the first-year trials. The aim is to standardize the data coming from different MENA countries so to ease data analysis and further results publication. This report has undergone several changes as it was being written and fed with the necessary data coming from the coordinators of each MENA country partner.

1. Introduction

Agronomic trials include a set of experimental trials to be conducted through MENA countries over two consecutive cropping years from M6 to M31 with the production of two deliverables D5.1 and D5.2. In the current report, we plan to develop a practical, simplified and comprehensive guide that partners involved in WP5 should follow for setting up, monitoring and collecting data from the agronomic trials to be carried out on ancient grains during the first-year trials. The aim is to standardize the data coming from different MENA countries so to ease data analysis and further results publication.

A total of 9 internal meetings were held to establish guidelines during the period May 2024 – January 2025. A first draft was already available in June 2024 and the final document has been provided through this deliverable. Here are contained guidelines on different topics such as Standardization of Protocols, Cooperation and Data Sharing, Risk Reduction, Facilitation of International Relations, Addressing Regional Challenges, Strengthening Research and Innovation. The guideline consists of four sections, each describing the best practices for setting up different types of agronomic trials i) Agronomic trials, ii) Disease trials, iii) Multiplication plots, iv) Ancient grains authentication.

2. The trials

During the year 1, three kinds of on-station trials are to be conducted through MENA countries. The first aims to explore robustness and adaptation of ancient grains to different environments and management level. The second is related to the disease resistance and disease incidence on their productivity; and the last set of trials are related to ancient grains authentication.

Guidelines are explained in Sections 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, and 2.4.

By the time of writing the experimental sites have been already identified, set up, and trials already started.

3 in Jordan, 4 in Egypt, 2 in Morocco, and 4 in Tunisia were established as experimental sites, as it is possible to consult from the table and figure below:

Country	Location Name	City/Region	Latitude	Longitude
Jordan	Maru station	Irbid	32,6135	35,9176
	Mushaqar Center	Madaba	31,7737	35,8025
	Rabba Center	Karak	31,3084	35,7624
Egypt	Sakha Agricultural Research Station	Sakha	31,1117	30,9458
	El Gemmiza Agricultural Research Station	El Gemmiza	30,867	31,028
	Nubaria Agricultural Research Station	Nubaria	30,6973	30,66713
	Side Agricultural Research Station	Side	29,076	31,097
Morocco	Marchouch	Marchouch	N.A.	N.A.
	Sidi Alaydi	Sidi Alaydi	N.A.	N.A.
Tunisia	INRAT experimental station	Tunis	36,8447	10,1925
	Bourabia experimental station	Bourabia	36,5981	10,1297

Marja experimental station	Boussalem	36,534	8,9529
Chebika experimental station	Kairouan	35,6211	9,9358

Table 1: SEEDS experimental sites

Figure 1: SEEDS experimental sites maps (Jordan, Egypt, Morocco, Tunisia)

2.1. Guidelines for on-station agronomic trials

2.1.1. The protocol

Plant material consists of “n” ancient cereal genotypes (AG) along with one modern cereal cultivar (MC). The suggested experimental design is a Strip plots with two factors:

- Horizontal factor: consists of two technical management systems: Low input versus high in put management package
- Vertical factor: the different cereal genotypes randomly assigned to each sub-block
- The number of Blocks (replications) is fixed to a minimum of 3 and a maximum of 5.

NB.

- It should be mentioned that a separate experimental protocol is required for each cereal species, if there is more than one species.
 - It is strongly recommended that agronomic trials to be carried out on a previous legume crop, or even a fallow.
 - the higher the number of repetitions, the greater the precision of the experiment.
- ### 2.1.2. Experimental units’ size and design.

It was agreed that experimental units’ size should not be neither too large nor too small. Each experimental unit contains **6 lines of 4 m long, and 25 cm apart**. Each experimental Station must comprise 6 to 8 (3 to 4 replications by 2 management systems) experimental units (EU) for each ancient cereal genotype/species considered.

2.1.2. Basics for designing low or high cropping systems

Management system is defined as a combination of several production factors at different application levels/rates. It must be defined for each MENA country separately according to the grain potential of ancient grains, weed and disease pressure, irrigation versus rain-fed, targeted seeding density etc. (Table 2).

Criteria	Values for low input	Value for High input
Targeted seeding density	Targeting 150 grains/m ²	300 grains /m ²
Weeding	using herbicides targeting only broad leaf weeds if any	Targeting systematically broad leaf and grass weeds
Nitrogen rate	Targeting a grain yield of 2.5 T /ha, based on initial soil analysis*, overall, it is advisable to not exceed 66 kg N/ha) with split application (at two times)	Targeting 3.5 T/ha based on initial soil analysis. We may reach 100 kg N/ha with a split application (3 times)
Disease	apply fungicide only under potential risk of fungal disease incidence	Systematic application of fungicides in opportune times
Irrigation (if applied)	Deficit irrigation (reach up to 75% of the cereal needs at each water application)	Full irrigation (reach 100% of cereal needs) at each water application)

Table 2: Criteria for defining low and high cropping system

*: The yield caps may vary between MENA countries

Trial information related to the number of experimental sites, number of species and cultivars of ancient grains are given in Table 3.

MENA Partner	Number of experimental stations	Number of species	Species	Number Control	Number of ancient grain genotypes included in agronomic trials
Tunisia (INRAT)	3	2	Durum wheat	1	5
			Barley	1	1
Egypt (ARC)	3	1	Bread wheat (fully irrigated)	1	6 to 8
Jordan (NARC)	2	2	Durum wheat	2	7
			Barley	2	4
Morocco (IAV)	2	2	Durum wheat	2	5
			Barley	2	5

Table 3: Number of Experimental sites and ancient grains genotypes per each MENA country

2.1.3. Parameters to measure/monitor

In table 3 below, we report all potential parameters to measure or monitor during the whole cycle.

Weather parameters	Soil parameters	Physiological parameters	Agronomic Parameters
1) T_{min} , T_{max} , T_{avr} (daily)	7) T_{min} , T_{max} in soil (0-40 cm) *8) Soil moisture* (0-40 cm)	13) NDVI (3 times a year): Normalized Difference Vegetation Index**	17) Emergence rates
2) Hr_{min} , Hr_{max} , Hr_{avr}	9) pH (one time)	14) Leaf Area index	18) phenology (using Zadoks scale, Zadoks et al., 1974)

3) Rainfall (daily basis)	10) pH* (0-20 cm)	15) WUE (physiologic): parameters to monitor: Stomatal conductance, leaf vapor pressure deficit, Evapo- transpiration**	
4) Radiation (duration)			
5) Wind speed and Direction: each day hour			20) Agronomic-Scores (Lodging at Soft dough stage, winter vigor (Zadoks 31, spring vigor at Zadoks 60) 21) Grain yield on the 4 median lines of each EU 22) grain yield components: - Average number of heads per m ² on 2 linear meters per plot excluding border lines - number of kernels per head) on 30 spikes randomly chosen on median lines 23) straw yield 24) key disease scores at different intervals (0-9) 25) Harvest index (HI)
6) Potential Evapo- transpiration (mm)	11) Soil conductivity*(0-5 cm) 12) Surface soil temperature* (0- 5cm)	16) Temperature of vegetation cover with appropriate equipment if available **	

Table 4: Parameters and variables to measure/monitor on agronomic trials

*: the measure periodicity is to be fixed further with link to WP7.

** : Optional

2.1.4. Indicative Experimental Design

An indicative experimental design is given in Figure 2. Final Blocks layout would be dictated by the field reality and circumstances.

2.1.5. Data table

INRAT recommend registering all information related to all implemented trials as suggested in Table 4 below. We also recommend using the following form (Table 5) to collect data from experimental trials. It is based on the indicative experimental protocol. A separate form should be used for each experimental station. The suggested sheet should be modified according to the number of genotypes used.

Agronomic trials information				
	Site 1	Site 2	...	Site "n"
Location/Site
Year
Preceding crop
Seedbed preparation	Brief description of the various operations undertaken till seeding day			
Seeding date
Organic fertilizer	Organic manure type, rate, date of application			
Fertilizer during seeding	Fertilizer type, rate, date of application			
Fertilizer top dressing	Fertilizer type, rate, date of application			
Herbicides application	Herbicide commercial name, ai's, rate (g ai/ha), date of application, way of application			
Fungicide application	Herbicide commercial name, ai's, rate (g ai/ha), date of application, way of application			
Harvest	Date of harvest, how,			

Table 5: Agronomic Trial information sheet

D5.1 Agronomic trial best practices guidelines

Figure 2: Strip plot Experimental design for on-station Agronomy trials, year 1 at MENA countries

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Agronomic trial data table						SEEDS Project				
						Year			
						Country :	'Country-name'			
						Site	'Site_name'			
						Date			
Entry	Row	Column	Cropping system	Genotype	Block	Parameter 1	Parameter 2	...	Parameter n	
1	1	1	Low_i	C1	1					
2	1	2	Low_i	C2	1					
3	1	3	Low_i	C3	1					
...	1					
4	1	4	Low_i	C n	1					
5	1	5	Low_i	C 2	2					
6	1	6	Low_i	C 1	2					
7	1	7	Low_i	C n	2					
...	1					
8	1	8	Low_i	C 3	2					
9	1	9	Low_i	C n	3					
10	1	10	Low_i	C 2	3					
11	1	11	Low_i	C 1	3					
...	1					
12	1	12	Low_i	C n	3					
13	1	13	Low_i	C 3	4					
14	1	14	Low_i	C 2	4					
15	1	15	Low_i	C n	4					
...	1					
16	1	16	Low_i	C1	4					
17	2	16	High_i	C 3	4					
...	2	...	High_i					
18	2	15	High_i	C 1	4					
19	2	14	High_i	C 2	4					
20	2	13	High_i	C n	4					
21	2	12	High_i	C 3	3					
...	2	...	High_i					
22	2	11	High_i	C 1	3					
23	2	10	High_i	C n	3					
24	2	9	High_i	C 1	3					
25	2	8	High_i	C1	2					
...	2	...	High_i					
26	2	7	High_i	C 2	2					
27	2	6	High_i	C 3	2					
28	2	5	High_i	C n	2					
29	2	4	High_i	C 1	1					
...	2	High_i					
30	2	3	High_i	C n	1					
31	2	2	High_i	C 3	1					
32	2	1	High_i	C 2	1					

Table 6: Data table for data collection from agronomic field trials

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2.1.6. Sensors for crop monitoring

ITENE has been responsible for selecting the suitable commercially available sensors for crop monitoring to be used by INRAT, INGC, IAV, ARC and NARC.

As per the meeting held on July 9th, 2024, it was agreed on the purchase of one static sensor to be installed in one out of the 4 MENA countries and 4 mobile sensors that will rotate at regular, well-defined frequencies between all experimental stations in each country. The static sensor installed in an experimental station it will record the soil pH, temperature and moisture at a given frequency and data will be migrated to CERTH for the SEEDS platform algorithm functioning (See D7.1). For mobile sensors, a suitable measurement frequency is fixed to two weeks.

The purpose of each of these measurements is explained below:

Electrical conductivity (EC):

Purpose: Conductivity measures the amount of soluble salts (such as calcium, magnesium, sodium, among others) in the soil. A high conductivity indicates that the soil has a high concentration of salts, which could negatively affect the uptake of water and nutrients by plants. A low conductivity suggests that the soil is low in salts and is more suitable for most plants.

Uses: Helps determine soil salinity, which is critical for agriculture, as some plants are sensitive to high salt levels.

Water content:

Purpose: Measuring the amount of water present in the soil is crucial for assessing whether plants are receiving sufficient moisture for growth. Water content influences nutrient availability, seed germination and photosynthesis.

Uses: This measurement allows irrigation to be adjusted to ensure that the soil is neither too dry nor too wet, which can lead to drainage problems or root diseases.

Soil temperature:

Purpose: Temperature affects microbial activity, decomposition of organic matter and seed germination. Soil that is too cold or too warm can inhibit plant growth.

Uses: It allows farmers and gardeners to know soil conditions to optimize planting or irrigation timing. It is also important for determining the best time to plant certain crops.

Soil pH:

Purpose: Soil pH indicates whether the soil is acidic, neutral or alkaline. This factor affects the availability of nutrients, as certain nutrients are more easily accessible in specific pH ranges.

Uses: It helps farmers understand whether the soil needs to be amended with lime (to increase the pH) or with sulphur (to reduce it), which facilitates plant growth by ensuring that nutrients are in their most assimilable form.

In short, measuring these parameters provides a comprehensive understanding of soil conditions and allows informed decisions on irrigation management, fertilization, and agricultural practices.

Given the importance of quantifying the parameters described above in order to improve crop efficiency, as part of this project, in particular in WP3, equipment for measuring these parameters has been selected to be sent to the different partners so that they can characterize the soil and, based on the results, implement target solutions to improve the efficiency of the target crops. The following table shows the technical characteristics of the different selected equipment that has been sent to the collaborators for research purposes in this project:

VOLUMETRIC WATER CONTENT	VOLUMETRIC WATER CONTENT / CONDUCTIVITY / TEMPERATURE	PH SENSOR																																																																																																																																				
Supplier; LAB FERRER	Supplier; AT	Supplier: METTLER TOLEDO																																																																																																																																				
<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th colspan="2">Volumetric Water Content (VWC)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Mineral soil calibration:</td> <td>0,00 - 0,70 m³ / m³ soil</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Apparent dielectric permittivity (ε_a):</td> <td>>1 (air) to 80 (water)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Resolution:</td> <td>0.0010 meters³ / meter³</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Accuracy:</td> <td>Generic calibration: ±0.03 m³/m³ (±3.00% VWC) typical in mineral soils having solution EC < 8 dS/m</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Media Specific Calibration:</td> <td>±0.01-0.02 m³/m³ in any porous media</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Mineral soil calibration:</td> <td>±0.03 m³/m³ typical in mineral soils having solution EC < 8 dS/m</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Apparent dielectric permittivity (ε_a):</td> <td>1-40 (ground range), ±1 ea (unitless) 40-80, 15% of measurement</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Dielectric measurement frequency:</td> <td>70 MHz</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Temperature:</td> <td>Range: -40 to 60 °C Resolution: 0.1 °C Accuracy: ±1 °C</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Electrical Conductivity (EC):</td> <td>Range: 0 to 20 dS/m (volume) Resolution: 0.001 dS/m Accuracy: ±1.5% ±0.01 dS/m from 0 to 10 dS/m ±1.8% from 10 to 20 dS/m</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Exit:</td> <td>DDI series or SDI-12 communication protocol</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Dimensions:</td> <td>Length: 5.1cm Width: 2.4cm Height: 7.5cm</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Datalogger Compatibility:</td> <td>METTER dataloggers (DL6, EMS10) series or any data acquisition system capable of 4 to 15 VDC and serial or SDI-12 communication.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Cable length:</td> <td>5m (standard) 3.5mm stereo plug or stripped and tinned cables</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Supply voltage (VCC) to GND:</td> <td>Minimum: 4.0 VDC Maximum: 15.0 VDC</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Measurement duration:</td> <td>Minimum: 25 ms Maximum: 50 ms</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Volumetric Water Content (VWC)		Mineral soil calibration:	0,00 - 0,70 m ³ / m ³ soil	Apparent dielectric permittivity (ε _a):	>1 (air) to 80 (water)	Resolution:	0.0010 meters ³ / meter ³	Accuracy:	Generic calibration: ±0.03 m ³ /m ³ (±3.00% VWC) typical in mineral soils having solution EC < 8 dS/m	Media Specific Calibration:	±0.01-0.02 m ³ /m ³ in any porous media	Mineral soil calibration:	±0.03 m ³ /m ³ typical in mineral soils having solution EC < 8 dS/m	Apparent dielectric permittivity (ε _a):	1-40 (ground range), ±1 ea (unitless) 40-80, 15% of measurement	Dielectric measurement frequency:	70 MHz	Temperature:	Range: -40 to 60 °C Resolution: 0.1 °C Accuracy: ±1 °C	Electrical Conductivity (EC):	Range: 0 to 20 dS/m (volume) Resolution: 0.001 dS/m Accuracy: ±1.5% ±0.01 dS/m from 0 to 10 dS/m ±1.8% from 10 to 20 dS/m	Exit:	DDI series or SDI-12 communication protocol	Dimensions:	Length: 5.1cm Width: 2.4cm Height: 7.5cm	Datalogger Compatibility:	METTER dataloggers (DL6, EMS10) series or any data acquisition system capable of 4 to 15 VDC and serial or SDI-12 communication.	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Mineral soil calibration:	0,00 - 0,70 m ³ / m ³ soil																																																																																																																																					
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Accuracy:	Generic calibration: ±0.03 m ³ /m ³ (±3.00% VWC) typical in mineral soils having solution EC < 8 dS/m																																																																																																																																					
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Temperature:	Range: -40 to 60 °C Resolution: 0.1 °C Accuracy: ±1 °C																																																																																																																																					
Electrical Conductivity (EC):	Range: 0 to 20 dS/m (volume) Resolution: 0.001 dS/m Accuracy: ±1.5% ±0.01 dS/m from 0 to 10 dS/m ±1.8% from 10 to 20 dS/m																																																																																																																																					
Exit:	DDI series or SDI-12 communication protocol																																																																																																																																					
Dimensions:	Length: 5.1cm Width: 2.4cm Height: 7.5cm																																																																																																																																					
Datalogger Compatibility:	METTER dataloggers (DL6, EMS10) series or any data acquisition system capable of 4 to 15 VDC and serial or SDI-12 communication.																																																																																																																																					
Cable length:	5m (standard) 3.5mm stereo plug or stripped and tinned cables																																																																																																																																					
Supply voltage (VCC) to GND:	Minimum: 4.0 VDC Maximum: 15.0 VDC																																																																																																																																					
Measurement duration:	Minimum: 25 ms Maximum: 50 ms																																																																																																																																					
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ARC	ARC	ARC
	IAV	IAV
	INRAC	INRAC
	NARC	NARC

Table 7: Commercially available sensors for crop monitoring

2.2. Guidelines for disease trials

2.2.1. The protocol

The aim of this experimental trial is to reveal the impact of fungal diseases on the agronomic performances of ancient grains when grown in a low-input management system. The suggested experimental design is a strip plot with two factors:

- **Horizontal factor:** Disease management with two levels, artificially Inoculated treatments versus protected plots. Protected treatment means a systematic application of appropriate fungicide so that to prevent the onset of the targeted disease.
- Vertical factor: the different cereal genotypes randomly assigned to each sub-block
- The number of replications is fixed to 4
- Units size is to be fixed to 1.5 m x 4 m
- Distance between plots is to be maintained wide enough (1-2 m) to minimize collateral contaminations
- The low input systems are to be defined for each country partners separately

NB. When seeds quantities are not sufficient enough, it is suggested to conduct disease trials in pots under greenhouse conditions but following the same suggested experimental design as in field trial.

2.2.2. Number of Experimental sites

Trial information related to the number of experimental sites, number of species and cultivars of ancient grains to be used in Disease trials, are given in table 8.

MENA Partner	Number of experimental stations	Grain species	Key disease	Number Control/Checks	Number of ancient grain genotypes included in Disease trials
Tunisia (INRAT)	1	Durum wheat	Tan spot	1	6
Egypt (ARC)	1	Bread wheat	Stripe rust Leaf rust Stem rust	1	6-8
Jordon (NARC)	1	Durum wheat	Powdery mildew (there is a need to identify the races)	2	6
Morocco (IAV)	1	Barley	Net blotch	2	5

Table 8: Number of Experimental sites and ancient grains genotypes per each MENA country

2.2.3. Parameters to measure/monitor

In table below, we report all potential parameters to measure or monitor during the whole cycle.

Weather parameters	Soil parameters	Physiological parameters	Agronomic Parameters	Disease Parameters
1) T_{min} , T_{max} , T_{avr} (daily)	7) T_{min} , T_{max} in soil (0-40 cm) ✓	11) NDVI (3 times a year): Normalized Difference Vegetation Index	14) Emergence rates	19) key disease scores at different intervals* (0-9) 20) AUDPC (to be defined)
2) Hr_{min} , Hr_{max} , Hr_{avr}	8) Soil moisture ✓ (0-40 cm)	12) Leaf Area index	15) phenology (using Zadoks scale) 16) Agronomic-Scores (Lodging at Soft dough stage, winter vigor (Zadoks 31, spring vigor at Zadoks 60)	
3) Rainfall (daily basis)	9) pH (one time)	13) Temperature of vegetation cover	17) Grain-Yield 18) grain yield components (Average number of heads per m ² , 1000-Kernel, number of kernel per head)	
4) Radiation (duration)	10) Soil conductivity ✓		23) straw yield	
5) Wind speed and Direction				
6) Potential Evapo-transpiration (mm)				

2.2.4. Disease Scoring

Disease severity due to the key fungi will be assessed through visual scoring of disease symptoms on plant leaves, using the scale established by Saari-Prescott (1968) cited by Eyal et al. (1987). This scale is graded from 0 to 9, with each score corresponding to a level of severity and percentage of leaf coverage by disease symptoms. Scoring began as soon as the first symptoms of Tan spot appears on the leaves of the most susceptible genotype after artificial inoculation. From these visual notations, the MDI (Mass Disease Index) is calculated according to the following formula:

$$MDI_i = \left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^{10} (n \times i)}{N \times 9} \right) \times 100$$

With:

- n: number of plants with score i
- N: total number of plants scored for disease.

Based on the estimated MDIs, the Area Under Disease Progress Curve (AUDPC) is calculated using the formula:

$$AUDPC = \sum_{i=1}^n \left[\left(\frac{MDI_{i+1} + MDI_i}{2} \right) \times (T_{i+1} - T_i) \right]$$

With:

T_i = Time (in days) at the i^{th} notation.

N = Total number of notations

2.2.5. Indicative Experimental Design

An indicative experimental design is given in figure 3. Final Blocks layout would be dictated by the field reality and circumstances and the exact number of considered ancient grains genotypes.

In this case we can rely on the same data table presented in Table 9 to collect data from the trials.

2.2.6. Data table

We recommend using the forms indicated in figure 4 to collect data from disease experimental trials. It is based on the indicative experimental protocol. The suggested sheet should be modified according to the number of genotypes used.

2.2.7. References

Eyal Z, Breeding for resistance to Septoria and Stagonospora diseases in wheat. In J. A. Lucas, P. Bowyer, & H. M. Anderson (Eds.), *Septoria in cereals: a study of pathosystem*. 1999; 332–344.

D5.1 Agronomic trial best practices guidelines

Figure 3: Strip plot Experimental design for on-station Disease trials, year 1 at MENA countries

The SEEDSproject is part of the PRIMA Programme supported By the European Union under the Grant Agreement number 2332

Disease trial data table

SEEDS Project

Year
 Country
 Site

Seeding date
 Disease
 Inoculation date

Entry	Row	Column	Treatment	Genotype	Block	Date	Date	Date	Date	Date	Date	
						Score 1	Score 2	Score 3	Score 4	Score 5	Score 6	Score 7
1	1	1	Inoculated	G1	1							
2	1	2	Inoculated	G2	1							
3	1	3	Inoculated	G3	1							
...	1	1							
	1	4	Inoculated	Gn	1							
	1	5	Inoculated	G1	2							
	1	6	Inoculated	G2	2							
	1	7	Inoculated	G3	2							
	1	2							
	1	8	Inoculated	Gn	2							
	1	9	Inoculated	G1	3							
	1	10	Inoculated	G2	3							
	1	11	Inoculated	G3	3							
	1	3							
	1	12	Inoculated	Gn	3							
	1	13	Inoculated	G1	4							
	1	14	Inoculated	G2	4							
	1	15	Inoculated	G3	4							
	1	4							
	1	16	Inoculated	Gn	4							
	2	16	Protected	G1	1							
	2	...	Protected	G2	1							
	2	15	Protected	G3	1							
	2	14	Protected	1							
	2	13	Protected	Gn	1							
	2	12	Protected	G1	2							
	2	...	Protected	G2	2							
	2	11	Protected	G3	2							
	2	10	Protected	2							
	2	9	Protected	Gn	2							
	2	8	Protected	G1	3							
	2	...	Protected	G2	3							
	2	7	Protected	G3	3							
	2	6	Protected	3							
	2	5	Protected	Gn	3							
	2	4	Protected	G1	4							
	2	...	Protected	G2	4							
	2	3	Protected	G3	4							
	2	2	Protected	4							
n	2	1	Protected	Gn	4							

Table 9: Data table for data collection from Disease trials

The SEEDS project is part of the PRIMA Programme supported
 By the European Union under the Grant Agreement number 2332

2.3. Guidelines for authentication trials: distinctness, homogeneity and stability

2.3.1. Guideline Objective

This test Guideline is applicable to all varieties of *Triticum aestivum* and *T. turgidum* L. and *Hordeum vulgare*.

2.3.2. Required Material:

At least 100 ears of each wheat genotype are required. The ears should be well developed and not obviously affected by any pest or disease. They should contain a sufficient number of viable seeds to establish a satisfactory number of rows of plants to make observations.

2.3.3. Tests carrying out

1. The minimum duration of tests should normally be two similar growing periods/seasons.
2. The tests should normally be conducted at one site. If any important characteristics of the variety cannot be seen at that site, the variety may be tested at an additional location.
3. The field tests should be carried out under conditions ensuring normal growth.
4. The ears should be planted in separate 100 rows 1.5 meters long and 25 cm apart.

2.3.4. Methods and Observations

For the assessment of the characters uniformity on single ear-rows, the number of aberrant ears/rows, plants or parts of plants should not exceed 3%.

2.3.5. Characteristics and Symbols

1. To assess Distinctness, Uniformity and Stability, the characteristics and their states should be used.
2. Notes (1 to 9), for the purposes of electronic data processing, are given opposite the states of expression for each characteristic.
3. Legend: (*) Characteristics that should be used on all varieties in every growing period over which examinations are made and always be included in the variety descriptions. The optimum stage of development for the assessment of each characteristic is indicated by a number in the second column. The stages of development denoted by each number are described at the end of this text.

The letters indicate the following:

M: actual measurement

VG: visual assessment by a single observation of a group of plants or parts of plants

VS: visual assessment by observations of a number of individual ear- rows, plants or plant parts.

Table of Characteristics for *Triticum turgidum* (Durum wheat)

N°	Characteristics	Stage (Zadoks scale)	Expression for each characteristic	Note
1	Coleoptile: anthocyanin coloration	09..11 VS	absent or very +T7:V47weak	1
			weak	3
			medium	5
			strong	7
			Very strong	9
2	Plant: growth habit	25-29 VG	Erect	1
			semi-erect	3
			intermediate	5
			semi-prostrate	7
			prostrate	9
3	Frequency of plants with recurved flag leaf	47-51 VG	absent or very low	1
			low	3
			medium	5
			high	7
			very high	9
4	Time of ear emergence	50-52 VG	early	3
			medium	5
			late	7
5	Flag leaf: anthocyanin coloration of auricles	49-51 VG	absent or very weak	1
			Weak	2
			Medium	3
			Strong	4
			Very strong	5
6	Flag leaf: glaucosity of sheath	60-65 VG	absent or very weak	1
			Weak	3
			medium	5
			Strong	7
			Very strong	9
7	Flag leaf: glaucosity of lower side of leaf blade	60-65 VG	absent or very weak	1
			Weak	3
			medium	5
			Strong	7
8	Culm: density of hairiness of uppermost node	60-69 VG	absent or very weak	1
			Weak	3
			medium	5
			Strong	7
9	Culm: glaucosity of neck	60-65 VG	absent or very weak	1
			Weak	3
			medium	5
			Strong	7
			Very strong	9

Table of Characteristics for *Triticum turgidum* (Durum wheat). Continued 1.

N°	Characteristics	Stage (Zadoks scale)	Expression for each characteristic	Score
10	Ear: glaucosity	60-69 VG	absent or very weak	1
			Weak	3
			Medium	5
			Strong	7
11	Plant: length	75-92 M	very short	1
			Short	3
			medium	5
			Long	7
12	Ear: distribution of awns	80-92 VS	awnless	1
			tip awned	2
			halfawned	3
			fullyawned	4
13	Ear: length of awns at tip relative to length of ear	80-92 VS	shorter	1
			Equal	2
			Longer	3
14	Lower glume: shape	80-92 VS	Ovoid	1
			medium oblong	2
			narrow oblong	3
15	Lower glume: shape of shoulder	80-92 VS	sloping	1
			rounded	2
			straight	3
			elevated	4
			elevated with a 2nd beak	5
16	Lower glume: width of shoulder	80-92 VS	Very narrow	1
			narrow	3
			medium	5
			broad	7
			alternative type	2
			spring type	3
17	Lower glume: length of beak	80-92 VS	very short	1
			Short	3
			medium	5
			Long	7
18	Lower glume: curvature of beak	80-92 VS	absent	1
			Weak	3
			moderate	5
			strong	7

Table of Characteristics for *Triticum turgidum* (Durum wheat). Continued 2.

N°	Characteristics	Stage	Expression for each characteristic.	Score
17	Lower glume: length of beak	80-92 VS	very short	1
			Short	3
			medium	5
			Long	7
18	Lower glume: curvature of beak	80-92 VS	absent	1
			Weak	3
			moderate	5
			strong	7
19	Lower glume: hairiness of external surface	80-92 VS	absent	1
			present	9
20	Straw: pith in cross section	80-92 VS	Thin	1
			medium	3
			Thick	5
21	Awn: colour	80-92 VG	white	1
			light brown	2
			medium purple	3
			darkpurple	4
22	Ear: length (excluding awns)	80-92 VS	short	3
			medium	5
			Long	7
23	Ear: coloration	90-92 VG	white	1
			Slightly colored	2
			Strongly colored	3
24	Ear: density	80-92 VS	Lax	3
			medium	5
			dense	7
25	Grain: length of brush hair	92 VS	short	1
			medium	3
			Long	5
26	Grain: shape	92	Slightly elongated	1
			Moderately elongated	2
			Strongly elongated	3
27	Grain: coloration with phenol	92 VS	absent or very light	1
			Light	3
			Medium	5
			Dark	7
28	Plant: seasonal type	VG	winter type	1
			Spring type	2

Table of Characteristics for *Hordeum vulgare* (Barley)

N°	Character	Stage	Expression for each characteristic.	Score
1	Kernel: color of aleurone layer	VG/A	whitish	1
			light grey blue	2
			dark grey blue	3
			purple	4
			black	5
2	Plant: growth habit	VG/B	erect	1
			semi-erect	3
			intermediate	5
			semi-prostrate	7
			prostrate	9
3	Plant: intensity of green color	VG/B	light	1
			medium	2
			dark	3
4	Lowest leaves: hairiness of leaf sheath	VG/A	Absent	1
			present	9
5	Flag leaf: anthocyanin coloration of auricles	VG/B	absent or very weak	1
			weak	3
			medium	5
			strong	7
			Very strong	9
6	Flag leaf: attitude	VG/B	erect	1
			Semi-erect	3
			horizontal	5
			semi-reflexed	7
			reflexed	9
7	Time of ear emergence	MG/B	early	3
			medium	5
			late	7
8	Flag leaf: glaucosity of sheath	VG/B	absent or very weak	1
			weak	3
			medium	5
			strong	7
			Very strong	9
9	Awns: anthocyanin coloration of tips	VG/B	absent or very weak	1
			weak	3
			medium	5
			strong	7
			Very strong	9
10	Ear: glaucosity	VG/B	absent or very weak	1
			weak	3
			medium	5
			strong	7

Table of Characteristics for *Hordeum vulgare* (Barley). Continued 1.

N°	Characteristics	Stage	Expression for each characteristic.	Score
11	Ear: attitude	VG/B	erect	1
			Semi-erect	3
			horizontal	5
			semi-drooping	7
			drooping	9
12	Grain: anthocyanin coloration of nerves of lemma	VG/B	absent or very weak	1
			weak	3
			medium	5
			strong	7
			Very strong	9
13	Plant: length	MG/B	short	3
			medium	5
			long	7
14	Ear: number of rows	VG/B	two	1
			six	2
15	Ear: development of sterile spikelets	VG/B	none or rudimentary	1
			full	2
16	Sterile spikelet: attitude	VG/B	parallel	1
			parallel to divergent	2
			divergent	3
17	Ear: shape	VG/B	strongly tapering	1
			slightly tapering	2
			parallel	3
			fusiform	4
18	Ear: density	MS/B VG/B	sparse	3
			medium	5
			Dense	7
			Very dense	9
19	Ear: length	MS/B VG/B	short	3
			medium	5
			long	7
20	Awn: length	MS/B VG/B	Very short	1
			short	3
			medium	5
			long	7
21	Rachis: length of first segment	MG A/MS A/VG/A	short	3
			medium	5
			long	7
22	Rachis: curvature of first segment	VG/A	absent or very weak	1
			weak	3
			medium	5
			strong	7

Table of Characteristics for *Hordeum vulgare* (Barley). Continued 2.

N°	Characteristics	Stage	Expression for each characteristic.	Score
23	Median spikelet: length of glume and its awn relative to grain	VG A	shorter	1
			equal	2
			slightly longer	3
			much longer	4
24	Grain: rachilla hair type	VG A	short	1
			long	2
25	Grain: spiculation of inner lateral nerves of dorsal side of lemma	VG A	absent or very weak	1
			weak	3
			medium	5
			strong	7
26	Grain: type	VG A	non-husked	1
			husked	9
27	Grain: hairiness of ventral furrow	VG A	absent	1
			present	9
28	Lemma: shape of base	VG A	non-bevelled	1
			bevelled	2
29	Seasonal type	VG	winter type	1
			Alternative type	2
			Spring type	3

2.3.6. References

Zadoks J C., Chang T T et Konzak C F. 1974. A decimal code for the growth stage of cereals, Weed Res. 14: 415-421.

2.4. Guidelines for seeds multiplication

Seed multiplication is a necessary first step to initiate the transfer of the best genotypes to farmers. We plan to start multiplication from ancient grain spikes to ensure genotypes authenticity. As On-Farm trials would be established in year 2 (M21), seeds are to be multiplied during year 1. It is planned to start with at least 800 ears to be multiplied under favorable conditions or irrigated to ensure good grain production. Based on this hypothesis, 800 ears would produce 2 kg of seeds (under normal growing conditions) which can be sown on an average area of 200 m² in M9, from which we can estimate to produce in average up to 50 kg of seeds. This amount of seeds is capable of sowing 5000 m², which would allow for the sowing of 1,000 m² in at least 5 farms.

Number of spikes to start with	Average grain weight (g per 1000 grains)	Average number of grains/spike	Yield per spike (g)	Total grain to produce (kg)
500	50	50	2,5	1,25
600	50	50	2,5	1,5
700	50	50	2,5	1,75
800	50	50	2,5	2

3. Dissemination of key findings and best practices from agronomic trials

Two events will be held in each MENA country to disseminate the results of the conducted agronomic trials to farmers, especially during the first season. These events may be conducted in the field as participatory selection days or indoors through presentations and discussions of the key findings. Each country will select the most effective approach to ensure a successful transfer of results. A best practices box will also be designed for on-station and on farm agronomic trials.

Conclusions

These guidelines presented the protocols for three types of agronomic trials previously planned within the framework of WP5. Its objective is to harmonize protocols among the four MENA countries involved, thereby facilitating the presentation and publication of results. By following a rigorous methodology—from defining objectives to analysing results—the agronomists of the SEEDS team can generate reliable and actionable data to optimize yields, improve resource management, and promote agroecological agriculture based on ancient cereals.

